
**“ IMPROVING THE QUALITY MANAGEMENT OF PUBLIC EDUCATION
THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY”**

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Abstract.

This article has been written about digital technologies in education covering the current aspects and importance of use on a theoretical basis, he made his recommendations gave.

Keywords.

manage, management, digital technology, lesson, internet, decree, decision, education system. management of digital technology.creative

The progress of the comprehensive reforms carried out in our republic is direct the education system also shows its positive effects. The definition of comprehensive in the field with the aim of achieving even higher efficiency in all branches implementation of reforms, implementation of international experiments and innovative technologies in the context of today's new game is gaining importance. Because, of each sphere it is the development, knowledge, perception, thinking and qualifications of Representatives or specialists in this field and how much experience of advanced foreign countries in the same direction is defined by the identity.

That is why the next day of our motherland and its solid foundation it is important to pay special attention to the education and upbringing of the young generation of the creator is significant. Therefore, educational in all aspects of social life to instill aspects in the knowledge of young people and make the new Uzbekistan's future to what extent is the education of young generation who are owners of today's modern education system depending on the development. For this reason, it is also necessary to radically update the national education system finding alternative solutions and introducing them into practical activities is the main goal of each of us.

To what extent our above goals have been achieved, it is important to understand in society by providing consistency, adding innovative technologies

and national and international pedagogical experiences to the field, we give our young people a thoughtful perspective, scientific observations which serve to form an independent thought and a broad worldview based on motivating ideas the conditions are related to the fact that they are created. To do this, interact with the education system communication, integration provision and theoretical and practical in all areas of the system it is necessary to pay more attention to the processes that matter.

Actually, the quality modern education is a sustainable economic growth, Science, the development of technology and technology is a guarantee of ensuring the quality of social services came. Therefore, the priority of public policy in our country is focusing as one of the ways is getting stronger day by day. Especially today our state of development of the industry through the introduction of digital technologies into the system of education in the day it is considered as the main goal of its policy of our country.

Nowadays, the renewal and improvement of the educational system in our Pedagogical scientist in this regard M. M. Kholmukammedov developed his own "professional education system based on modern approaches in his article on "modernization": "the system is at the intersection of Regions and territories before itself training of secondary personnel capable of making a worthy contribution to economic growth, train young people to ensure the well-being of life through skilled labor, labor innovative and creative approach to activity, creativity, intellectual adds tasks such as development, "

To the above tasks promoted by Kholmukammedov in the case of relying, It is advisable to define the main objectives of the education system. In fact, the main functions of the education system in the conditions of today's new growth are content the fact that he gets rich, his social tasks improving modern education. Such that one of the social tasks is the application and use of digital technologies in education in itself all the components of the formation of competencies of members development of embodied strategies, the beginning of the system in today's information age it is necessary to organize the purpose.

Our president Sh.Mirziyoyev: "...new for the development of the country being able to take the initiative and implement them out onto the field with ideas, training of new generation personnel of intellectual and educational potential, educational organizations graduates have the necessary skills and knowledge in them to become modern professionals formation;

National education system that can withstand today's fierce competition at the world level to improve your approach, textbook and study requirements based on the requirements of the Times, creating a new generation of them, optimizing learning programs and standards;

Improving the role and status of the executive staff, educators and mentors of educational institutions, professorships and representatives of the fields of Science in our society, material depending on the worthy appreciation of their hard work and the effectiveness of the activity promotion;

Regular improvement of professional skills and efficiency of activities of pedagogical workers create the necessary conditions to go, "read throughout life" the system of professional development improving on the principle of;

Education in the field of modern information and communication technologies creation of a system for automation and comprehensive analysis of control, electronic further development of resources and distance education, in the IT field among education recipients popularization of professions;

Information and communication technologies during the new development of our country automation of education management, electronic resources, and remote education through application further development, to popularize it-area professions among education recipients special attention is paid by the head of State, Digital in the education system it shows how high the importance and importance of technology is.

It is difficult to imagine our daily life without information communication technologies, computers and the Internet in the era when today's globalization process is taking place. Hence for even today, digital technologies are gradually developing all of our daily lives entering its spheres it is becoming an integral part of social life. Exactly, that's it taking into account the important aspect, more than 10 techniques and digital in our country. in addition, to the activities of higher educational institutions that train specialists in the direction of technology the addition of digital technologies is not only in areas such as economics, politics, but also, it is a sign that it is also of great importance in the education system.

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From our above points, one can conclude that in a system of Education the use of digital technologies, first, to ensure the effectiveness of the transition, secondly, various illustrations on lesson processes, video rollers, visual aids, preparation of handouts, and thirdly, multimedia of teacher-educators products, computer techniques, the use of Internet tools and their use in the course of the lesson support serves to improve skills.

Training teachers in the use of digital technology creation of a continuous methodological service system aimed at formation; rational and targeted use of digital technologies and education to classes organized on the basis of digital technologies of participants in the process it is required to follow the necessary recommendations, such as the formation of adaptability

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